

Change – The transformative power of citizen science

Does crowdsourced transcription data increase accessibility for blind and low vision users?

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Abstract

Many crowdsourcing and citizen science projects are conducted collaboratively by galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAMs) and research teams, and result in transcription data that could be helpful to blind and low vision users. Through usability and accessibility testing with blind and low vision scholarly users, we identify changes to GLAM systems and data sharing that can increase crowdsourcing, citizen science, and GLAM data discovery and utility for many blind and low vision users.

Keywords: assistive technology, cultural heritage, digital humanities, print-disability, usability.

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Published by NHM, BOKU and ECSA and peer-reviewed under responsibility of ECSA-ÖCSK-2024 (Change – The transformative power of citizen science)

Introduction and landscape review

Volunteer crowdsourced transcription is a common method of data generation in citizen science and often engages a coalition of academics, cultural heritage practitioners from Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAMs), and the public. Hundreds of GLAMs around the world collaborate in or run their own crowdsourced transcription projects to produce new datasets for research, and searchable text to create accessible pathways to digital images of source materials. For example, “[Project PHaEDRA: Preserving Harvard’s Early Data and Research in Astronomy](#)” at Harvard’s Wolbach

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Library, utilizes both Zooniverse and the Smithsonian Transcription Center (STC) to engage volunteers in transcription.

In a review of data practices by citizen science, community science, and crowdsourcing practitioners and researchers, Bowser et al (2020) found that while “many projects demonstrated willingness to make their data available” inappropriate data licensing, and insufficient provision of accessible formats for human and machine users create significant barriers to data access and reuse. Machine-readability is vital for assistive technologies, such as screen readers, Braille keyboards and other Braille devices. When crowdsourced data is not accessible to machines, it is not accessible to people who are blind or low vision (BLV) and use assistive technologies to access data, web content, and research results.

GLAMs have a core mission to make their collections publicly available, discoverable, and usable, and therefore could be central to addressing the problems Bowser et al (2020) identified. The STC, and the By the People (BTP) transcription project at the Library of Congress (USA), explicitly state that crowdsourced transcription makes collections accessible for BLV people (Ferriter et al. 2019; Haynes et al. 2019), and the BTP team report that volunteers are passionate about this mission (Shelton, 2021). Yet, while GLAM practitioners actively solicit transcriptions to improve accessibility for BLV users, research by Xie et al. (2018; 2020) suggests that the complexity of digital library systems poses significant challenges to data discovery for BLV users, which, we hypothesized, may persist even when crowdsourced transcriptions are integrated.

We present a subset of findings from Crowdsourced Data: Accuracy, Accessibility, Authority (CDAAA), a 3-year grant project to investigate whether GLAMs experience sociotechnical barriers to integrating crowdsourced transcriptions with discovery systems and whether transcription content is accessible to BLV users. We limit our discussion to RQ3 (Accessibility): “When transcription data is successfully integrated with a GLAM discovery system is it accessible to BLV people who use assistive technologies?”

This analysis focuses on crowdsourced transcriptions from Shakespeare’s World, a collaboration between Zooniverse, the Folger Shakespeare Library, and the *Oxford English Dictionary* (2015–2019) that generated crowdsourced transcriptions of 12,578 single and double-page spreads of handwritten manuscripts from the 1600s–1700s. The transcriptions were intended to enhance the discovery and accessibility of Folger collections and produce textual datasets for digital humanities, history of science, and Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) research, and surface new words, usages and variants for the *OED* (Van Hying 2019; Van Hying and Jones 2021).

Methods

Between February and June 2024, we conducted 12 blended accessibility and usability interviews over Zoom with BLV academics who use GLAM systems for their work (duration ~120-minutes). The think-aloud protocol draws on user-experience and human-computer interaction research (Aizpurua et al. 2016; SUS protocol 2013; Lam et al. 2021; Schaadhardt et al. 2021); cultural heritage and disability studies (Lazar et al. 2017). 10 discovery systems for 9 GLAM organizations were tested; each was tested by 4 people.

We tested two Folger systems due to a data migration (March 2024). Participants performed three tasks for each of 3 GLAM systems:

1. locate the GLAM website;
2. locate transcriptions of any kind;
3. locate a specific transcription (Fig. 1).

Systems were tested in a counterbalanced order. 1 blind participant tested the Folger system Luna. 2 blind participants and 1 low vision participant tested its successor, Islandora (Table 1; N=4).

page 63 [numbered from back]: Damson Wine receipt

Full View Pages Page

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DOWNLOAD [Permalink: https://digitalcollections.folger.edu/img54775](https://digitalcollections.folger.edu/img54775)

Item Description	Transcription
midn Piffards receipt for Elder wine 63	
Take 20 pound of malaga reasons dried them and put them into six gallons of spring water 9 or 10 dayes then dreyne of water clean from them turn it into a vessell When you turne it put into it three pints of the Juice of Elder berries being full ripe stop it up close to worke and a bout a month after bottle it.	
line divider	
damson wine	
the worst	
in the world	
to 4 pound of fruit take 2 quartes of water and a pound of sugar lett the water and sugar boile together till no hark, acum arises then put in your fruit and lett it gently boile till your wine have a tinkle then rune it through a hare sieve when its cold bottle it.	
to 4 pound of fruit take 2 quartes of water and a pound of sugar lett the water and a pound of sugar lett the	

Figure 1. Folger Shakespeare Library manuscript and unedited transcription of wine receipts, <https://digitalcollections.folger.edu/img54775>. Islandora. Search prompt “worst in the world.”

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Data from the 3 participants who tested the Folger Shakespeare Library systems.

ACC Tester ID	Blind or low vision	T1: Can you navigate to the Folger Shakespeare Library's website?	T2: Search for digitized materials i.e. images of manuscripts with transcriptions	T3: Search for "The worst in the world"	Rate statement: "This discovery system website is easy to use" (strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat disagree, strongly disagree)	Rate statement: "This website meets my needs as a user." (strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat disagree, strongly disagree)	LAM CMS test position
ACC-3	B	Complete Success	Failure	Success with minor issues	Agree	Agree	1
ACC-7	LV	Complete Success	Failure	Success with minor issues	Agree	Agree	2
ACC-9	B	Complete Success	Success with major issues	Success with minor issues	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	3
ACC-12	B	Complete Success	Failure	Success with major issues	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	1

Participants were unaware of the availability of crowdsourced transcriptions in general, and were unfamiliar with searching for transcriptions through GLAMs. All participants found the Folger website (T1) easily but struggled with T2. Each user navigated Folger CMSs with some frustration, but ACC-3 and ACC-7 agreed with the statement "This system is easy to use" and thought it would meet their needs if they used it regularly. All emphasized the need for consistent page, filter, and search layouts. ACC-3 observed that for "screen reader users [...] it's like looking through a straw. Right? You don't see the whole thing. You just see exactly where you are right now."

ACC-3 and ACC-9 switched from screen readers to Braille keyboards to investigate the transcription after encountering insertions and deletions like "worst in the world", which they likened to "track-changes." The said transcription convention information would be helpful. ACC-7 could see deletions, but not the fainter "worst in the world". Transcription conventions including the question marks used by Zooniverse volunteers to indicate uncertainty were confusing. When asked to interpret duplicate lines (Fig. 1, final lines) ACC-7 speculated the original author was "probably not thinking and just writing quickly [...] or they were intoxicated themselves." The duplicates originate in aggregation difficulties on Zooniverse, but this information is missing.

Conclusion

Crowdsourced data holds great promise for accessibility of the scientific and cultural heritage record, but only if the content is discoverable, well structured, and well described. Standard fields and consistent system layout are vital for BLV users to navigate GLAM systems, confirming previous analysis of library systems by Xie et al (2018; 2020). Transcription data should include information about the conventions used, i.e.

insertions, deletions, original spelling, markup, and degree of editing, so users can understand how transcriptions relate to original texts. Finally, GLAMs and crowdsourcing teams could increase the impact of their projects by reaching out to BLV users about the existence and availability of the resulting data.

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